

Behaviour of heavy metals and their management to remediate and avoid agricultural soil contamination

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Behaviour Of Heavy Metals And Their Management To Remediate And Avoid Agricultural Soil Contamination

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COOPERATIVE RESEARCH CENTRE FOR CONTAMINATION ASSESSMENT AND REMEDIATION OF THE ENVIRONMENT

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AGRICULTURE IN INDONESIA

- Agriculture- one of the key economic driver's in Indonesia;
- Significant decline in its contribution towards Gross Domestic Product during the last 50 years- nevertheless it remains major income generator for Indonesian families
- 2013: contributed 14.43% towards national GDP- compared to 15.19% in 2010
- Jobs- for 49 million people which equals 41% of the country's total workforce
- Current: 30% of Indonesia's land area is used for agriculture– regulated by the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture

Google image

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CONTAMINANT SOURCE IN INDONESIAN AGRICULTURE

- Industrial Pollution
 - Textile industry;
 - Other manufacturing industries
 - Active and legacy mines
 - Solid wastes, waste waters- applications
- Oil Pollution
 - Fossil fuels
 - Old service stations etc;
- Agricultural pollution
 - Pesticides;
 - Fertilizers
 - Metals,
 - Nutrients
- Geogenic

FAO, 2015

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SOIL CONTAMINATION IN INDONESIAN AGRICULTURE: case study

- Contamination from industrial wastes
 - Metal input via sewage sludge applications from textile industries- with this waste disposed directly into three rivers and contaminated water used for irrigation- 720 ha of rice land polluted
 - Elevated levels of B, Cd, Pb in soils from Rancaek- 3 districts (Kurnia, 1999)- impact to rice yield- declining from 4 to 6 mt/ha to 1 mt/ha;
 - High concentrations of Pb, Cr, Cd, Cu and B reported in rice plants

Kurnia, U., S. Sutono, Markus Anda, Sulaeman, A.M. Kumiawansyah, dan S.H. Tala'ohu. 2000. Pengkajian baku mutu tanah pada lahan pertanian. Laporan Akhir Kerjasama Penelitian Bapedal-Puslitbangtanak. (In Bahasa Indonesia)

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FOCUS OF PRESENTATION: CADMIUM

- Sources of Cadmium in Agricultural soils
 - Industrial wastes- including application of waste waters, sewage/biosolids;
 - Fertiliser phosphorus;
 - Geogenic- though to a limited extent
- Other contaminants of potential concern in agriculture are not heavy metals- As and F;
- Pesticides.

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CADMIUM CHEMISTRY IN SOILS

- Metals can be bound to soil surface;
- A proportion of metals can be free i.e. Not bound and this form of metal can pose threat to environmental and human health
- Soil solution composition influences Cd chemistry
 - forms soluble complexes with Cl^- and SO_4^{2-}
 - Forms insoluble CdS in paddy soils under reducing conditions;
 - Solubility is largely pH dependent;
 - Similar in chemistry to Zn and so can substitute for Zn in Zn deficient soils
 - Ionic radius similar to Ca^{2+} so can substitute for Ca^{2+} in/on minerals, root uptake, etc.

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Managing Heavy Metal(oid)s

IMMOBILIZATION OR BIOAVAILABILITY REDUCTION

- Liming;
- Organic additions;
- Biochar;
- Precipitation.

Liming reduces plant availability of metals

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Organic amendments reduce metal(loid) toxicity in mine tailings (Moreno et al., 2005)

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USING BIOCHAR TO REDUCE METAL AVAILABILITY

- Biochar is a fine-grained, highly porous charcoal substance that is distinguished from other charcoals in its intended use as a soil amendment.
- Biochar is charcoal that has been produced under conditions that optimize certain characteristics deemed useful in agriculture, such as high surface area per unit of volume and low amounts of residual resin

Hunt et al. (2010) The Basics of Biochar: A Natural Soil Amendment. Soil and Crop Management

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Mechanism of metal sorption to Biochars

In addition to biochar surface-metal interactions, biochar changes soil properties-pH

Beesley et al., 2015: Biochar and heavy metals. In: Lehmann, J. and Joseph, S. (eds.) Biochar for environmental management: science, technology and implementation. 2nd ed. Earthscan, London, pp. 563-594. ISBN 9780415704157 www.crcrcare.com

Mode of action of Biochar

Biochar:

- Immobilises metals;
- Reduces phyto-toxicity;
- Improves biomass;
- Improves soil physical properties

Beesley et al., 2015: Biochar and heavy metals. In: Lehmann, J. and Joseph, S. (eds.) Biochar for environmental management: science, technology and implementation. 2nd ed. Earthscan, London, pp. 563-594. ISBN 9780415704151 www.crccare.com

Immobilization of cadmium and lead using phosphate: approach for site specific metal contamination

Using phosphate to immobilise cadmium

Effect of phosphate on tissue Cd content

Effect of phosphate on tissue Cd content

- ✓ Phosphate addition decreased Cd bioavailability thereby reducing metal(loid) phytotoxicity (Bolan *et al.*, 2003)

*With phosphate
low Cd in plants*

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IN SITU REMEDIATION- PHYTO-REMEDICATION

- Using phyto-accumulators;
- Enhancing uptake by mobilizing metals
- Caution: ensure that mobilization couples uptake otherwise potential for leaching of metals into subsurface and ultimately ground water

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SOIL AMENDMENTS FOR MOBILIZATION

- EDTA: Chelation of metals;
- Thiosulphate: complexation of mercury;
- Cyanide: complexation of gold
- Phosphate: Mobilization of As

the $[Cu(EDTA)]^{2-}$ ion

The chelation and complexation reactions are largely controlled by soil chemistry – pH and Eh

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CONCLUSIONS

- Presence of toxic metals is a key concern given its potential for bioaccumulation by plants posing risks to human health
- Managing toxic substances present in agricultural land can be challenging-
- For Cd, lime has been and still is the most preferred option with Zn and cultivar selection as other options;
- A trans-discipline approach that takes into consideration nature of soils, soil properties and strategies that lead to bioavailability reduction

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